

PRO-SIS

Sviluppo e disseminazione di algoritmi per il progetto delle innovative strategie di protezione sismica "CONSTRAIN" e applicazione pilota su edifici esistenti in muratura

Razvoj in diseminacija postopkov za projektiranje inovativnega načina potresnega utrjevanja obstoječih zidanih stavb "CONSTRAIN"

Report 2.3
Procedura per la
progettazione degli
interventi di rinforzo

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PRO-SIS

Development and dissemination of procedures for designing an innovative way seismic strengthening of existing masonry buildings "CONSTRAIN"

Report 2.3 *Design of seismic strengthening* **CONSTRAIN**

NOVEMBER 2025

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Report 2.3

Design of seismic strengthening CONSTRAN

Summary

1. Introduction	2
2. Design procedure	3
2.1. Inspection of the existing structure	3
2.2. Obtaining required material parameters	5
2.3. Modelling of structures	6
2.4. Modelling of structural components for in-plane loads	8
2.4.1. Piers	8
2.4.2. Spandrels	15
2.5. Interpretation of results and presenting compliance criteria	22
2.6. Local behaviour (out-of-plane)	24
3. Examples	26
3.1. Piers	26
3.1.1. Calculations	26
3.1.2. Comparison to the experiment	29
3.2. Spandrels	31
3.2.1. Calculations	31
3.2.2. Comparison to the experiment	34
Acknowledgments	35
References	35
Appendix A - List of symbols	36

1. Introduction

The report collects the results of Activity 2.3 of the PRO-SIS project, aimed at the Definition of the procedure required for designers to correctly and effectively plan the intervention strategies proposed in “CONSTRAIN”.

Within the CONSTRAIN project (INTERREG V-A ITALIA-SLOVENIA 2014-2020 - <https://2014-2020.ita-slo.eu/it/constrain>), strategies to reduce the seismic vulnerability of existing masonry were developed and tested in an extensive experimental campaign. The strengthening method developed is based on the use of mortar coatings reinforced with fibre-based composite materials. The main advantage of this system is that it can be applied to only one side of the wall, making it much more convenient for residents and businesses. As construction work can be carried out only on the exterior of the building, people and their belongings do not have to be relocated, and business activity does not have to be interrupted. Furthermore, valuable artistic decorations can be preserved on the interior (or exterior, when interior application is preferred). The strengthening method stands out due to its proven effectiveness in tests on structural components and a full-scale pilot building.

The aim of the “PRO-SIS” project (INTERREG VI-A ITALIA-SLOVENIA 2021-2027 - <https://www.ita-slo.eu/it/pro-sis>) is to develop the necessary methods for designing and applying these strategies. To this end, the design procedures have been developed based on analytical and numerical analyses calibrated against the experimental results of “CONSTRAIN”. The results provide designers with robust strategies for designing the proposed systems, as well as instructions for design in commonly used commercial structural design programmes.

This report presents the design procedure to apply the CONSTRAIN strengthening method. The strategy for defining the parameters to be used in the analysis are outlined. The document includes also solved examples. The results of this work also become a part of the PRO-SIS Guidelines (PRO-SIS Report 2.4).

2. Design procedure

The design procedure for applying the CONSTRAIN strengthening method shall be articulated in the following main phases:

- Inspection of the existing structure;
- Definition of the required material parameters;
- Modelling of the structure;
- Interpretation of results and presenting compliance criteria.

These steps are described in detail in the following.

2.1. Inspection of the existing structure

Before any strengthening is planned, a structural engineer must inspect the building. The inspector should be provided with all existing documentation and given access to all areas relevant to the structural inspection. Information about past modifications to the structure should be obtained, possibly by interviewing residents or the owner. Generic data sources such as contemporary codes, standards, and documented practice can also be used. The inspector may propose to the owner that destructive or non-destructive tests be carried out to obtain the material parameters required for the structural assessment.

The engineer should write a report on the field investigations and measurements. The report should include the following information:

- Date of construction and any potential past renovations;
- Description of the building and its structural system;
- Description of the materials used;
- Description of the condition of the structure and a report on any observed damage;
- Data on the foundations and soil conditions at the site.

Potential damage, such as cracks, should be measured and documented. Most importantly, the cause of the cracks should be identified and a solution for repair should be proposed. Finally, any differences from the original plans should also be reported.

Based on the latest draft version of new generation of Eurocode 8-3 (Design of structures for earthquake resistance - Part 3: Assessment and retrofitting of buildings and bridges) the knowledge level (KL) about the structure is determined separately for:

- geometry (KLG);
- materials (KLM);
- structural details (KLD).

The knowledge level depends on the availability of documentation and the amount and quality of field surveys. There are three levels of knowledge (KL1, KL2, KL3), with KL1 being the lowest and KL3 the highest. To reach a certain KL, a specific number of surveys must be conducted. Further information about this is provided in the code. The purpose of the KL is to determine

the values of safety factors and criteria for the inspecting engineer. For example, the lowest KL (KL1) is required for the assessment of a single-family house, whereas for a hospital, the highest KL (KL3) should be achieved.

In practical terms, the *geometry* can be checked by simple measurements for regular masonry structures, while for monuments or structures with complex layout the geometry can be obtained by laser scanning (high-definition surveying – HDS).

Regarding *structural details* in masonry structures, it is crucial to determine whether the tying of the structure is present and sufficient. Inspectors should check:

- Connections between floors and walls (e.g., whether wooden joists are tied to the walls or not);
- The presence of ties in the walls (such as steel bars at floor levels in walls or floors);
- The strength and rigidity of the floors (floors should be rigid in their plane to ensure seismic load distribution between all walls; old wooden floors are not sufficient).

To determine material parameters, the inspector should examine the typology of the masonry, the type of bricks or stones, the quality of mortar, and the quality of construction. Preferably, samples can be tested in the laboratory or in situ by destructive or non-destructive tests. The design values for strength verification should be obtained by reducing the characteristic or mean strength with a material safety factor. The procedure for obtaining material parameters is further explained in the next section.

The visual inspection of the structure is a crucial step of the field survey. The inspector should inspect the following properties of masonry:

- Type and texture of masonry (stone, brick, regular, irregular, etc.).
- The general state of masonry (physical/chemical degradation of bricks, material defects, alteration).
- Problems with localized degradation (molds, efflorescence, presence of climbing plant etc).
- Presence of irregularities in the masonry (flue tiles, tracks, etc.).
- Different material or different construction techniques.
- Change of original structure (opening/closing windows/doors, reduction of wall thickness and presence of concrete beams inside a wall etc.).
- Wrong or obsolete reinforcement.

2.2. Obtaining required material parameters

For historic masonry structures, there is usually very little original documentation and no information about material quality. The preferred and most reliable method for obtaining material parameters is always testing, either in situ or on samples extracted for laboratory analysis. For important structures that require a high KL, such as hospitals or schools, this approach is mandatory. Various tests are available. It is common to take brick samples, either whole or cores, and mortar samples for laboratory testing. More advanced, but less frequently used, methods include single or double flat jack tests to measure the stress, strength, and elastic modulus of masonry, as well as shove tests or diagonal compression tests to measure the shear strength of masonry.

For less important structures, testing may be prohibitively expensive or complicated, and in such cases, alternative approaches can be used. One method is to obtain this information from nearby structures built in the same period and had material properties.

A popular and convenient method is to find the information in a database. In Slovenia, the most popular source is the book by Prof. Tomažević (Potresno odporne Zidane stavbe, Tehnis 2009). In Italy, a good source is the masonry database (<https://www.abacomurature.it/>). If none of the above sources is available, some values can usually be found in the codes (e.g., Eurocode, the Ministerial Circular correlated to the Italian National Building Code [1]-[2]).

The data required for seismic verification of existing buildings are:

- Elastic modulus.
- Shear modulus.
- Compressive strength.
- Shear strength (or tensile strength in diagonal compression).

2.3. Modelling of structures

When modelling masonry structures, it is necessary to create models to estimate the seismic resistance of the structure to in-plane loads, typically by constructing a global model of the structure, and to estimate the resistance of individual walls or parts of the structure to out-of-plane loads. In this section, the modelling of the entire structure to estimate the global response is presented. The modelling to estimate the out-of-plane response is presented in section 3.4.

The most common approach to modelling masonry structures for design and verification is the "Equivalent Frame Method" (EFM). This method is available in most commercial software for masonry structures, such as 3Muri, Midas Gen, PRO-SAP, and AMQUAKE.

The EFM assumes that walls are idealised by beam elements, as shown in Fig. 2.1a. Each beam represents the response of a wall segment, which is either pier, spandrel, or a rigid part of the wall. The segments are indicated by coloured areas in Fig. 2.1b: red areas represent rigid segments, grey areas are piers, and the dark yellow areas are spandrels. The pier height increases with the distance from the opening, at an angle of 30° (see Fig. 2.1a); this rule does not apply to spandrels. Further adjustments may be made to evaluate the effective pier height (i.e., the Dolce rule).

Fig. 2.1 Idealization of a wall according to Equivalent Frame Method.

The piers and spandrels exhibit a nonlinear response, which can represent different failure mechanisms, as explained in detail in section 2.4. The axes of the piers and spandrels are assumed to pass through the centre of gravity of the cross-section. The rigid segments are located at the massive joints between the piers and spandrels. These joints are typically so strong that damage is unlikely to occur there.

The structural model is typically three-dimensional, with floor structures modelled as either rigid or flexible diaphragms. Depending on the commercial software used for structural analysis, EFM models must be constructed manually by the user or are generated automatically from the structure's geometry. An example of the geometry of a 3D structural model and the corresponding generated EFM model is shown in Fig. 2.2.

Fig. 2.2 A 3D view of a masonry structure (a) and an EFM model (b) created in commercial software.

The EFM models are used to perform pushover analysis. In this analysis, the gravity loads are applied and kept constant, after which the lateral load is applied in a specific pattern (e.g., inverted triangle, according to the first vibration mode, constant, depending on the choice or software) and gradually increased until the structure collapses. The base shear as a function of the displacement at the control point (typically at the top of the structure) forms the pushover capacity curve, which can be compared to the demand on the structure to evaluate its response. To present the seismic load on the same graph, the design spectrum is plotted in acceleration-displacement format. Two approaches are commonly used: the N2 method or the Capacity Spectrum Method. This is further discussed in Section 2.4.

It should be noted that the EFM is suitable only for walls with a relatively uniform layout of openings. For structures with irregular patterns of openings, the method becomes less suitable and reliable. Thorough knowledge of the software, along with carefully considered and deliberate choices in model construction, is essential for obtaining reliable results.

2.4. Modelling of structural components for in-plane loads

The simplified procedure developed to calculate analytically the in-plane capacity curve of masonry piers and spandrels strengthened with CRM is described in the following. The list of symbols is provided in ANNEX A.

2.4.1. Piers

The pier is usually between two openings on one floor as shown in Fig. 2.1. The dimensions of the pier (Fig. 2.3a) are length (l_p), masonry thickness (t), mortar coating thickness (t_c) and pier height (h_p). The CRM coating covers the entire surface and extends vertically beyond the pier.

The piers are loaded by vertical compressive force N , and exhibit a nonlinear response to the horizontal load V_p , as indicated by the black line in Fig. 2.3b. In the design process the nonlinear response is idealised by several linear segments, represented by the red line in Fig. 2.3b. The idealised response is defined by four values, each presented in a separate subsection:

- The elastic stiffness, $K_{p,e}$.
- The maximum resistance of pier to lateral force, V_p .
- The maximum elastic displacement, $d_{p,y}$.
- The ultimate displacement, $d_{p,u}$.

Fig. 2.3 The geometry of the pier (a), and the response of the pier to in-plane lateral load at the top of the pier (b)

The model of the pier in the EFM structure is schematically shown in Fig. 2.4. It consists of a vertical elastic beam element and nonlinear hinges. The rotational hinges at the bottom and top of the element reproduce flexural failure, while the hinge at mid-height reproduces shear failure. The response of both types of hinges is assumed to be bilinear.

The numerical model is the same for unstrengthened piers (i.e., piers without coating). However, the properties of such piers are much lower.

Fig. 2.4 The numerical model of a pier in equivalent frame method

- **Elastic stiffness $K_{p,e}$**

The computer programs based on the EFM capture the stiffness of the element by taking into account deformability of the elastic beam elements (see Fig. 2.4). To get realistic deflections, the elastic and shear modulus of masonry must correspond to the actual properties of the materials. The relation between the stiffness and the material and geometric properties of the pier are shown in Eq. 3.1.

$$\frac{1}{K_{p,e}} = \frac{h_p^3}{\eta \cdot J \cdot E} + \frac{1.2h_p}{G \cdot l_p \cdot t} \quad (2.1)$$

with η coefficient for boundary conditions (e.g. $\eta = 12$ for fixed-fixed type boundary conditions and $\eta = 3$ for cantilever) and J second moment of area of the masonry cross-section.

For unstrengthened (URM) piers, the elastic and shear moduli correspond to the masonry material. In the case of coating, the values must be adjusted:

$$E = \frac{t E_m + t_c E_c}{t} \quad (2.2)$$

$$G = \frac{t G_m + t_c G_c}{t} \quad (2.3)$$

where E and G are the effective moduli of the pier (with coating), normalised to the original thickness of the masonry, t . E_m and G_m are the elastic and shear moduli of masonry, while E_c and G_c are the elastic and shear moduli of the mortar of the coating; t_c is the thickness of the coating.

All properties are evaluated with respect to the original thickness of the masonry (t), and it is not necessary to modify the geometry of the structure when moving from the unstrengthened to the CRM-strengthened configuration. The moment of inertia of the cross section remains the same, but the bending stiffness of the cross-section increases because E is higher than E_m .

In structural analysis, whether response spectrum analysis or pushover, the stiffness of the structure is reduced to account for cracked cross-sections. This reduction is typically achieved by reducing the elastic and shear moduli by a factor of 0.5.

- **Resistance to lateral force V_p**

The CRM-strengthened masonry pier, loaded by vertical force N and subjected to an in-plane lateral load can fail either in diagonal shear (at a force $V_{P,d(CRM)}$) or in flexure (at a force $V_{P,f(CRM)}$). The lower of the two resistances should be considered in design:

$$V_{P(CRM)} = \min(V_{P,d(CRM)}; V_{P,f(CRM)}) \quad (2.4)$$

The lateral resistance should also not exceed the strength of the compressed strut:

$$V_{P(CRM)} \leq 0.25 \cdot l_p \cdot t \cdot f_{m,cd} \quad (2.5)$$

In the case of diagonal shear failure, the lateral resistance $V_{P,d(CRM)}$ is the sum of the resistances of the unstrengthened masonry, $V_{P,d(URM)}$, and the fibre reinforcement, $V_{P,d(Fib)}$:

$$V_{P,d(CRM)} = V_{P,d(URM)} + V_{P,d(Fib)} \quad (2.6)$$

The Turnšek Čačovič model can be used to calculate the resistance of URM piers to diagonal shear:

$$V_{P,d(URM)} = \frac{f_{m,td}}{\beta} \cdot l_p \cdot t \sqrt{1 + \frac{\sigma_o}{f_{m,td}}} = \frac{1.5\tau_{0,d}}{\beta} \cdot l_p \cdot t \sqrt{1 + \frac{\sigma_o}{1.5\tau_{0,d}}} \quad (2.7)$$

where $f_{m,td}$ is the design tensile strength of masonry obtained by the diagonal compression test (or cyclic shear compression test). Italian guidelines [2] allow the use of $f_{m,t} = 1.5 \tau_0$, where τ_0 is the shear strength at zero precompression corresponding to diagonal cracking through irregular masonry. It should be noted that τ_0 differs from f_{v0} as defined in Eurocode 6, which corresponds to sliding shear along bed joints. $f_{m,t}$ and f_{v0} are therefore not directly related, as they describe physically different material models. β in equation (2.7) is the ratio between the peak and average shear stress in the cross-section, which is normally evaluated from the slenderness ratio $1 \leq h_p/l_p \leq 1.5$. The compressive stress in the cross-section, σ_o , is calculated as $N_{P,d} / (t \cdot l_p)$, where the design compressive force $N_{P,d}$ is calculated using the seismic load combinations.

The shear resistance provided by CRM coating is calculated on the assumption that only fibres contribute to the strength at the maximum resistance limit state. This is based on the observation that the mortar cracks well before the maximum resistance is reached, and its contribution to resistance at this stage is negligible.

The horizontal fibres (strands of fibres) that run across the assumed diagonal crack contribute to the resistance. The strength provided by the horizontal strands of fibres is ideally the fracture strength of the fibres. In the case of CONSTRAIN strengthening, fibre fracture is likely to occur. However, if different types of failure are expected (such as fibre pull-out or delamination of the coating from the wall), the strength of the fibres is reduced in the calculation by reducing the ultimate strain.

The formula for calculation of strength of the CRM coating:

$$V_{P,d(Fib)} = \chi \cdot \frac{1}{\gamma} \cdot i \cdot A_{Fib} \cdot n_{Fib} \cdot \alpha_T \cdot \epsilon_{lim,Fib,d} \cdot E_{Fib} \quad (2.8)$$

Where:

- χ is the reduction coefficient that considers if the coating is applied unsymmetrically: $\chi = 1$ if the coating is on both sides and $\chi = 0.7$ if coating is only on one side. *CONSTRAIN tests indicate χ could be equal to 1 also for one sided application*; however, the number of tests was limited.
- γ is the partial factor for the resistance model (normally =2).
- i is the number of strengthened sides (1 or 2).
- A_{Fib} is the net cross section of a strand of FRP material.
- n_{Fib} is the number of horizontal strands crossing the diagonal crack. It can be calculated as I_{Fib}/s , where s is the strand spacing and I_{Fib} is the reference dimension of the pier measured orthogonally to the shear force (the pier height, h_p). The CNR-DT 215/2018 guidelines for FRCM systems [3] specify a limit for I_{Fib} , assuming that cracks cannot be at a steeper incline than 45° (max I_{Fib} is not greater than the pier's length, l_p). *The CONSTRAIN tests showed that cracks can develop at a steeper angle*; however, the number of tests was limited.
- α_T is a reduction factor that accounts for the reduced tensile strength of the fibres when stressed in shear. The reduction factor is assumed to be $\alpha_T = 0.8$; *CONSTRAIN tests indicate that this reduction is not necessary*; however, the number of tests was limited;
- $\varepsilon_{im,Fib,d}$ is the design effective strain of the strands at failure. This value is obtained from lap shear tests and should be provided by the producer. *In the case of CONSTRAIN strengthening, this strain can be assumed equal to the ultimate strain at fracture*. The ultimate design strain can include reductions for exposure to aggressive environments (see [3] for details).
- E_{Fib} is the elastic modulus of the strands.

When checking the capacity of the pier in flexural failure, the resistance of a CRM strengthened masonry pier is calculated based on the following assumptions:

- composite action of CRM coating and masonry (monolithic cross-section);
- planar sections remain planar (Bernoulli hypothesis);
- zero tensile strength of masonry;
- bilinear response of masonry in compression (Fig. 2.5a);
- zero compressive strength of fibres;
- linear response of fibres in tension, up to fracture (Fig. 2.5b);
- the contribution of the mortar, in both tension and compression, is neglected;
- the effect of the asymmetry of the CRM coating is neglected (it can be implicitly taken into account by reduction coefficient χ applied to $\varepsilon_{im,Fib,d}$).

In the plots of constitutive laws in Fig. 2.5, the following notation is introduced: $\varepsilon_{m,y}$ is the strain of masonry at the elastic limit (i.e. conventional yielding), $\varepsilon_{m,u}$ is the ultimate strain of masonry, and $\varepsilon_{im,Fib}$ is the effective tensile strain of fibres at failure.

The problem of calculating the bending resistance at a given axial load is therefore very similar to designing a reinforced concrete section. Any software for cross-section design can be used if it supports the constitutive models shown in Fig. 2.5.

Fig. 2.5 The constitutive law of masonry (a) and of fibers (b).

If software is not available, analytical expressions may be used. The three cases are distinguished (Fig. 2.6), and the solution is the lowest of the three.

- *Type I*: masonry crushing at the compressive edge ($\epsilon_m = \epsilon_{m,u}$) and fibres in the elastic range ($\epsilon_{Fib} < \epsilon_{lim,Fib,d}$):

$$M_{P,Rd}^I = f_{m,cd} \frac{t y_n}{2} \left[l_p (1 - k) - y_n (1 - k)^2 + k \left(\frac{l_p}{2} - y_n + \frac{2}{3} k y_n \right) \right] + \frac{\epsilon_{m,u}}{y_n} E_{Fib} t_{Fib} \frac{(d_{Fib} - y_n)^2}{12} (2 y_n + 4 d_{Fib} - 3 l_p) \quad (2.9)$$

$$k = \frac{\epsilon_{m,y}}{\epsilon_{m,u}} \quad (2.10)$$

$$y_n = \frac{N_{P,d} - E_{Fib} t_{Fib} d_{Fib} \epsilon_{m,u} + \sqrt{N_{P,d}^2 + E_{Fib} t_{Fib} d_{Fib} \epsilon_{m,u} [(2 - k)t \cdot d_{Fib} f_{m,cd} - 2 N_{P,d}]}}{t f_{m,cd} (2 - k) - E_{Fib} t_{Fib} \epsilon_{m,u}} \quad (2.11)$$

- *Type II*: tensile fracture of fibres ($\epsilon_{Fib} = \epsilon_{lim,Fib,d}$) and masonry compressive strain in the plateau ($\epsilon_{m,y} \leq \epsilon_m \leq \epsilon_{m,u}$):

$$M_{P,Rd}^{II} = f_{m,cd} \frac{t}{12} \left[2 d_{Fib} y_n \xi (2 \xi + 3) + 3 l_p [y_n (2 + \xi) - \xi d_{Fib}] - 2 y_n^2 (\xi^2 + 3 + 3 \xi) - 2 \xi^2 d_{Fib}^2 \right] + \epsilon_{lim,Fib,d} E_{Fib} t_{Fib} \frac{d_{Fib} - y_n}{12} (2 y_n + 4 d_{Fib} - 3 l_p) \quad (2.12)$$

$$\xi = \frac{\epsilon_{m,y}}{\epsilon_{lim,Fib,d}} \quad (2.13)$$

$$y_n = \frac{2 \cdot N_{P,d} + t \xi f_{m,cd} \cdot d_{Fib} + E_{Fib} t_{Fib} d_{Fib} \epsilon_{lim,Fib,d}}{t f_{m,cd} (2 + \xi) + E_{Fib} t_{Fib} \epsilon_{lim,Fib,d}} \quad (2.14)$$

- *Type III*: tensile fracture of fibres ($\epsilon_{Fib} = \epsilon_{lim,Fib,d}$) and linear stress distribution of masonry in compression ($\epsilon_m < \epsilon_{m,y}$):

$$M_{P,Rd}^{III} = \frac{t E_m \epsilon_{lim,Fib,d}}{12} \frac{y_n^2}{d_{Fib} - y_n} (3 l_p - 2 y_n) + \epsilon_{lim,Fib,d} E_{Fib} t_{Fib} \frac{d_{Fib} - y_n}{12} (2 y_n + 4 d_{Fib} - 3 l_p) \quad (2.15)$$

$$y_n = \frac{N_{P,d} + E_{Fib} t_{Fib} d_{Fib} \epsilon_{lim,Fib,d} - \sqrt{N_{P,d}^2 + E_m \epsilon_{lim,Fib,d} d_{Fib} t (E_{Fib} t_{Fib} d_{Fib} \epsilon_{lim,Fib,d} + 2 N_{P,d})}}{\epsilon_{lim,Fib,d} (E_{Fib} t_{Fib} - t E_m)} \quad (2.16)$$

- $M_{P,Rd}$ is the design bending moment resistance of the pier;
- $N_{P,d}$ is the design axial (compressive) force of the pier;
- y_n is the depth of neutral axis;
- t is thickness of masonry;
- d_{Fib} is distance between extreme tension in strands and extreme compression in masonry;
- t_{Fib} is the equivalent thickness of the tensile layer = $i A_{Fib} / s$;
- i is the number of strengthened sides (1 or 2);
- A_{Fib} is the net cross section of a strand of FRP material;
- s is the strand spacing

The pier's lateral resistance associated to the in-plane bending failure is calculated as:

$$V_{p,f(CRM)} = \frac{\alpha M_{P,Rd(CRM)}}{h_p}, \quad (2.17)$$

where α is the parameter for the boundary conditions (e.g. $\alpha=1$ for fixed-fixed boundary conditions and $\alpha=2$ for cantilever boundary conditions).

Fig. 2.6 Strain and stress distribution into the CRM strengthened masonry cross section, for the three different cases.

It is observed that CRM strengthening increases the flexural capacity of the pier only if it is properly anchored or extended at the ends. Otherwise, the reinforcement is ineffective, and the flexural resistance is evaluated as for the unstrengthened configuration.

The flexural resistance of URM pier can be calculated by the following formula:

$$M_{P,Rd(URM)} = \sigma_0 \frac{t \cdot l_p^2}{2} \left(1 - \frac{\sigma_0}{0.85 f_{m,cd}} \right), \quad (2.18)$$

where $f_{m,cd}$ is the design compressive strength of masonry.

- **Elastic displacement $d_{p,y}$**

The elastic displacement $d_{p,y}$ (also called the conventional yield displacement) is calculated from the shear force V_p and the elastic stiffness $K_{p,e}$:

$$d_{p,y} = \frac{V_p}{K_{p,e}}. \quad (2.19)$$

- **Ultimate displacement $d_{p,u}$**

The codes and guidelines do not provide a direct answer. For reinforced masonry, which differs from CRM-strengthened masonry, the limits specified in the Italian codes [1] are $0.008 \cdot h_p$ for walls failing in shear and $0.016 \cdot h_p$ for walls failing in bending.

Tests show that for CONSTRAN strengthening, $d_{p,u} = 0.01 \cdot h_p$ can be used for piers failing in shear, and $d_{p,u} = 0.02 \cdot h_p$ can be used for piers failing in bending. This assumption is valid for walls strengthened on one or both sides. However, the number of tests was limited.

2.4.2. Spandrels

The spandrels are the horizontal elements between the piers, as shown in Fig. 2.1. Their primary function is to support the floor structures above windows and doors. Because masonry has almost no capacity for tensile loads, the spandrel is supported by a wooden lintel or a masonry arch. The spandrels can also provide a coupling effect to the piers.

The dimensions of the spandrel (Fig. 2.7a) are length (l_s), masonry thickness (t), mortar coating thickness (t_c), and height of the masonry part of the spandrel (h_s). The CRM coating covers the entire surface and extends beyond the spandrel.

The spandrels are not loaded axially and exhibit a nonlinear response to the lateral load V_s , as indicated by the black lines in Fig. 2.7c. During the design process, this nonlinear response is idealised by linear segments, shown by the red line in Fig. 2.7c. The idealised response is defined by four values, each presented in a separate subsection:

- The elastic stiffness, $K_{s,e}$;
- The maximum resistance of spandrel to lateral force, V_s .
- The maximum elastic displacement, $d_{s,y}$;
- The ultimate displacement, $d_{s,u}$.

Fig. 2.7: (a) The geometry of the spandrel, with (b) detail of forces acting on the spandrel and (c) the response of CONSTRAN strengthened the spandrel.

The model of the spandrel in the EFM structure is schematically shown in Fig. 2.8. It consists of a horizontal elastic beam element and nonlinear hinges. The rotational hinges at the lateral extremities of the element can reproduce flexural failure, while the hinge at the centre can reproduce shear failure.

Fig. 2.8 The numerical model of a spandrel in equivalent frame method.

- **Elastic stiffness $K_{S,e}$**

Computer programmes based on the EFM capture the stiffness of the element by considering the deformability of the elastic beam elements (see Fig. 2.9). To obtain realistic deflections, the elastic and shear moduli of masonry must correspond to the actual properties of the materials.

$$\frac{1}{K_{S,e}} = \frac{l_S^3}{\eta \cdot J \cdot E} + \frac{1.2 \cdot l_S}{G \cdot h_S \cdot t} \quad (2.20)$$

with η coefficient for boundary conditions (e.g., $\eta = 12$ for fixed-fixed boundary conditions and $\eta = 3$ for cantilever) and J , the second moment of area of the masonry cross-section.

For unstrengthened (URM) piers, the elastic and shear moduli correspond to the masonry material. In the case of coating, the values must be adjusted accordingly:

$$E = \frac{t \cdot E_m + t_c \cdot E_c}{t} \quad (2.21)$$

$$G = \frac{t \cdot G_m + t_c \cdot G_c}{t} \quad (2.22)$$

where E and G are the effective moduli of the spandrel (with coating), normalised to the original thickness of the masonry, t . E_m and G_m are the elastic and shear moduli of masonry, and E_c and G_c are the elastic and shear moduli of the mortar of the coating; t_c is the thickness of the coating.

All properties are evaluated with respect to the original thickness of the masonry (t), and it is not necessary to modify the geometry of the structure when moving from the unstrengthened to the CRM-strengthened configuration. The moment of inertia of the cross-section remains the same, but the bending stiffness increases because E is higher than E_m .

In structural analysis, whether response spectrum analysis or pushover, the stiffness of the structure is reduced to account for cracked cross-sections. This reduction is typically achieved by reducing the elastic and shear moduli by a factor of 0.5.

- **Resistance to lateral force V_S**

The CRM strengthened masonry spandrel subjected to in-plane load can fail either in diagonal shear (at a force $V_{S,d(CRM)}$) or in flexure (at a force $V_{S,f(CRM)}$). The lowest of the two resistances should be considered in design:

$$V_{S(CRM)} = \min(V_{S,d(CRM)}; V_{S,f(CRM)}) \quad (2.23)$$

The resistance should also not exceed the strength of the compressed strut:

$$V_{S(CRM)} \leq 0.25 \cdot h_s \cdot t \cdot f_{m,cd} \quad (2.24)$$

In the case of diagonal shear failure, the resistance $V_{S,d(CRM)}$ is the sum of the reduced resistance of unstrengthened masonry, $\lambda \cdot V_{S,d(URM)}$, and the resistance of fibre-based meshes, $V_{S,d(Fib)}$:

$$V_{S,d(CRM)} = \lambda \cdot V_{S,d(URM)} + V_{S,d(Fib)} \quad (2.25)$$

where $\lambda \leq 1$ is a coefficient accounting for the reduction of resistance after diagonal cracking in the masonry (= 0.6 for reinforced concrete or steel lintel, 0.4 for timber lintel, 0.1 for masonry arch).

The Turnšek Čačovič model can be used to calculate the resistance of URM spandrels to diagonal shear is:

$$V_{S,d(URM)} = \frac{f_{m,td}}{\beta} h_s \cdot t \sqrt{1 + \frac{\sigma_o}{f_{m,td}}} = \frac{1.5\tau_{o,d}}{\beta} h_s \cdot t \sqrt{1 + \frac{\sigma_o}{1.5\tau_{o,d}}}, \quad (2.26)$$

where $f_{m,td}$ is the design tensile strength of masonry obtained by the diagonal compression test (or cyclic shear compression test). Italian guidelines [2] allow the use $f_{m,t} = 1.5 \tau_o$, where τ_o is the shear strength at zero precompression corresponding to diagonal cracking through irregular masonry. It should be noted that τ_o differs from f_{v0} as defined in Eurocode 6, which corresponds to sliding shear along bed joints. $f_{m,t}$ and f_{v0} are therefore not directly related, as they describe physically different material models. β in equation (2.26) is the ratio between the peak and average shear stress in the cross section, which is normally evaluated from the slenderness ratio $1 \leq l_s/h_s \leq 1.5$ The compressive stress in the cross-section, σ_o , is calculated as $N_{s,d} / (t h_s)$, where the design compressive force $N_{s,d}$ is calculated using the seismic load combinations. However, it is usually assumed to be zero because of negligible axial force in the spandrel; in this case the square root term equals one.

The shear resistance provided by CRM coating is calculated on the assumption that only fibres contribute to the strength at the maximum resistance limit state. This is based on the observation that the mortar cracks well before the maximum resistance is reached, and its contribution to resistance at this stage is negligible.

The vertical fibres (strands of fibres) that run across the assumed diagonal crack contribute to the resistance. The strength provided by the vertical strands of fibres is ideally the fracture strength of the fibres. *In the case of CONSTRAIN strengthening, fibre fracture is likely to occur.* However, if different types of failure are expected (such as fibre pull-out or delamination of the coating from the wall), the strength of the fibres is reduced in the calculation by lowering the ultimate strain.

The formula for calculation of strength of the CRM coating:

$$V_{S,Fib} = \chi \frac{1}{\gamma} \cdot i \cdot A_{Fib} \cdot n_{Fib} \cdot \alpha_T \cdot \epsilon_{lim, Fib,d} \cdot E_{Fib} \quad (2.27)$$

where:

- χ is the reduction coefficient that accounts for whether the coating is applied unsymmetrically: $\chi = 1$ if the coating is on both sides and $\chi = 0.7$ if the coating is only on one

side. *CONSTRAIN tests indicate that χ could be equal to 1 for one or two sided application; however, the number of tests was limited;*

- γ is the partial factor for the resistance model (normally =2);
- i is the number of strengthened sides (1 or 2);
- A_{Fib} is the net cross section of a strand of FRP material;
- n_{Fib} is the number of vertical strands crossing the diagonal crack. It can be calculated as I_{Fib}/s , where s is the strand spacing and I_{Fib} the reference dimension of the spandrel measured orthogonally to the shear force (the spandrel length, l_s). The CNR-DT 215/2018 guidelines for FRCM systems [3] provide a limit for I_{Fib} , which assumes that cracks cannot be at a steeper incline than 45° (max I_{Fib} is not greater than the spandrel's height, h_s). *The CONSTRAIN tests showed that cracks can develop at a steeper angle; however, the number of tests was limited;*
- α_T is a reduction factor that accounts for the reduced tensile strength of the fibres when stressed in shear. The reduction factor is assumed to be $\alpha_T = 0.8$; *CONSTRAIN tests indicate this reduction is not necessary; however, the number of tests was limited;*
- $\varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d}$ is the design effective strain of strands at failure. This value is obtained by lap shear tests and should be provided by the producer. *In the case of CONSTRAIN strengthening, this strain can be assumed equal to ultimate strain at fracture.* The the ultimate design strain can include reductions for exposure to aggressive environment (see [3] for details).
- E_{Fib} is the elastic modulus of the strands.

When calculating the capacity of spandrels in flexural failure, the resistance of CRM strengthened masonry spandrels is calculated based on the following assumptions:

- composite action of the CRM coating and the masonry (monolithic cross-section);
- planar sections remain planar (Bernoulli hypothesis);
- zero tensile strength of masonry;
- bilinear response of masonry in compression (Fig. 2.9a);
- zero compressive strength of fibres;
- linear response of fibres in tension, up to fracture (Fig. 2.9b);
- the contribution of the mortar, in both tension and compression, is neglected;
- the effect of the asymmetry of the CRM coating is neglected (it can be implicitly accounted for by a reduction coefficient χ applied to $\varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d}$).

In the plots of constitutive laws (Fig. 2.9), the following notation is introduced: $\varepsilon_{m,y}$ is the strain of masonry at the elastic limit (i.e. conventional failure yielding), $\varepsilon_{m,u}$ is the ultimate strain of masonry, and $\varepsilon_{lim,Fib}$ is the effective strain of fibres at failure.

Fig. 2.9 The constitutive law of masonry (a) and of fibers (b).

The problem of calculating the bending resistance in the absence of axial load is therefore very similar to designing a reinforced concrete section. Any software for cross-section design can be used if it supports the constitutive models shown in Fig. 2.9.

If software is not available, analytical expressions can be used. The three cases are distinguished (Fig. 2.10), and the solution is the lowest of the three.

- *Type I*: masonry crushing at the compressive edge ($\varepsilon_m = \varepsilon_{m,u}$) and fibres in the elastic range ($\varepsilon_{Fib} < \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d}$):

$$M_{S,Rd}^I = f_{m,cd} \frac{t y_n}{2} \left[h_s (1 - k) - y_n (1 - k)^2 + k \left(\frac{h_s}{2} - y_n + \frac{2}{3} k y_n \right) \right] + \frac{\varepsilon_{m,u}}{y_n} E_{Fib} t_{Fib} \frac{(d_{Fib} - y_n)^2}{12} (2y_n + 4d_{Fib} - 3h_s) \quad (2.28)$$

$$k = \frac{\varepsilon_{m,y}}{\varepsilon_{m,u}} \quad (2.29)$$

$$y_n = \frac{N_{S,d} - E_{Fib} t_{Fib} d_{Fib} \varepsilon_{m,u} + \sqrt{N_{S,d}^2 + E_{Fib} t_{Fib} d_{Fib} \varepsilon_{m,u} [(2 - k)t \cdot d_{Fib} f_{m,cd} - 2N_{S,d}]}}{t f_{m,cd} (2 - k) - E_{Fib} t_{Fib} \varepsilon_{m,u}} \quad (2.30)$$

- *Type II*: tensile fracture of fibres ($\varepsilon_{Fib} = \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d}$) and masonry compressive strain in the plateau ($\varepsilon_{m,y} \leq \varepsilon_m \leq \varepsilon_{m,u}$):

$$M_{S,Rd}^{II} = f_{m,cd} \frac{t}{12} \left[2d_{Fib} y_n \xi (2\xi + 3) + 3h_s [y_n (2 + \xi) - \xi d_{Fib}] - 2y_n^2 \cdot (\xi^2 + 3 + 3\xi) - 2\xi^2 d_{Fib}^2 \right] + \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d} E_{Fib} t_{Fib} \frac{d_{Fib} - y_n}{12} (2y_n + 4d_{Fib} - 3h_s) \quad (2.31)$$

$$\xi = \frac{\varepsilon_{m,y}}{\varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d}} \quad (2.32)$$

$$y_n = \frac{2 \cdot N_{S,d} + t \xi f_{m,cd} \cdot d_{Fib,d} + E_{Fib} t_{Fib} d_{Fib} \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d}}{t f_{m,cd} (2 + \xi) + E_{Fib} t_{Fib} \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d}} \quad (2.33)$$

- *Type III*: tensile fracture of fibers ($\varepsilon_{Fib} = \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d}$) and linear stress distribution of masonry in compression ($\varepsilon_m < \varepsilon_{m,y}$):

$$M_{S,Rd}^{III} = \frac{t E_m \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d}}{12} \frac{y_n^2}{d_{Fib} - y_n} (3h_s - 2y_n) + \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d} E_{Fib} t_{Fib} \frac{d_{Fib} - y_n}{12} (2y_n + 4d_{Fib} - 3h_s) \quad (2.34)$$

$$y_n = \frac{N_{S,d} + E_f t_{Fib} d_{Fib} \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d} - \sqrt{N_{S,d}^2 + E_m \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d} d_{Fib} t_{Fib} (E_f t_{Fib} d_f \varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d} + 2N_{S,d})}}{\varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d} (E_{Fib} t_{Fib} - t E_m)} \quad (2.35)$$

- $M_{S,Rd}$ is the design bending moment resistance of the spandrel;
- $N_{S,d}$ is the design axial (compressive) force of the spandrel (usually assumed 0);
- y_n is the depth of neutral axis;
- t is thickness of masonry;
- d_{Fib} is distance between extreme tension in strands and extreme compression in masonry;
- t_{Fib} is the equivalent thickness of the tensile layer = $i A_{Fib} / s$;
- i is the number of strengthened sides (1 or 2);

- A_{Fib} is the net cross section of a strand of FRP material;
- s is the strand spacing.

Fig. 2.10 Strain and stress distribution in CRM strengthened masonry cross section for the three different cases.

The spandrel's resistance to in-plane bending failure is calculated as:

$$V_{S,f(CRM)} = \frac{\alpha M_{S,Rd(CRM)}}{l_s}, \quad (2.36)$$

where α is the parameter for the boundary conditions (e.g. $\alpha = 1$ for fixed-fixed boundary conditions and $\alpha = 2$ for cantilever boundary conditions). It is observed that CRM strengthening increases the flexural capacity of the spandrel only if it is properly anchored or extended over the ends. Otherwise, the reinforcement is ineffective, and the flexural resistance is evaluated as for the unstrengthened configuration (shown below).

The flexural resistance of URM spandrel is low and can be calculated using the following formulas:

$$M_{S,Rd(URM)} = \frac{2}{3} f_{t,eq} \cdot t \cdot h_b \cdot h_s \cdot \rho, \quad \text{with } \rho = h_s / 4h_b \quad (2.37)$$

where $f_{t,eq}$ is the equivalent tensile strength (Fig. 2.11), calculated as:

$$f_{t,eq} = \frac{l_{eff}}{h_b} (f_{v0} + 0.65 \cdot \sigma_{0P}), \quad (2.38)$$

where l_{eff} is the effective interlocking length, h_b the height of the brick, f_{v0} the shear strength at zero pre-compression, and σ_{0P} the average compressive stress in the adjacent piers. In the case of stone masonry, the values of the effective interlocking length and stone height may be assumed as average values, based on visual inspection of the masonry. In the case of poor masonry, the bending strength of the spandrel can be neglected.

When the flexural resistance is reached at $d_{s,y}$, vertical cracks appear at the spandrel ends and a sudden drop in resistance occurs (Fig. 2.11b). The residual strength after cracking due to friction is obtained by assuming $f_{v0} = 0$ in Eq. (2.38).

Fig. 2.11 Bending resistance mechanism in of unreinforced spandrel (a) and typical response to lateral load (b).

A masonry spandrel can benefit from the coupling effect of a horizontal tie element (such as a steel bar or a reinforced concrete beam), which provides the spandrel with strength and ductility. In this case, the bending resistance can be calculated the following formula:

$$M_{S,Rd(URM+tie)} = H_P \frac{h_S}{2} \left(1 - \frac{H_P}{0.85 f_{hm,cd} h_S t} \right), \quad (2.39)$$

where H_P is the minimum between the tensile resistance of the tie element and $0.4 \cdot f_{hm,cd} \cdot h_S \cdot t$, where $f_{hm,cd}$ is the design compressive strength of masonry in the horizontal direction.

- **Elastic displacement $d_{s,y}$**

The elastic displacement $d_{s,y}$ (also called conventional yield displacement) is calculated from shear force V_S and elastic stiffness $K_{S,e}$:

$$d_{s,y} = \frac{V_S}{K_{S,e}} \quad (2.40)$$

- **Ultimate displacement $d_{s,u}$**

The codes and guidelines do not provide a direct answer. However, according to the Italian guidelines [2], for spandrels with tensile-resistant devices (such as ties or CRM coating), the limits are $0.015 \cdot l_S$ for shear failure and $0.020 \cdot l_S$ for bending failure.

Tests shows that for *CONSTRAIN* strengthening, $d_{s,u} = 0.030 \cdot l_S$ can be used for spandrels failing in either shear or bending. This assumption is valid for walls strengthened on one or both sides. However, the number of tests was limited.

2.5. Interpretation of results and presenting compliance criteria

As mentioned in Section 2.2, the usual procedure for assessing the seismic resistance of masonry buildings, whether existing or strengthened, is to perform nonlinear pushover analysis.

The result of the pushover analysis is the capacity curve, which shows base shear (or acceleration) as a function of the displacement at the top of the structure. Additionally, a detailed state of the structure is obtained for each point on the pushover curve, indicating which elements are damaged, the extent of the damage, and whether the damage is due to shear or bending. An example is shown in Fig. 2.12, which depicts a structure under a particular lateral load. Elements marked with dark blue circles are undamaged, light blue elements are lightly damaged, orange elements are heavily damaged, and red elements have failed. Different colours or markings may be used depending on the software. Such graphical illustrations are crucial for identifying and quantifying damage in the structure.

Fig. 2.12 State of the structure at a particular level of horizontal load: (a) shear damage and (b) bending damage.

To compare the capacity curve of the structure with the seismic demand (inelastic spectrum in acceleration-displacement format), it must be converted into the response of a single-degree-of-freedom (SDOF) model. The procedure for this transformation is described in building codes (e.g., Eurocode 8-1, Annex B). The performance point corresponding to the attainment of a given performance criterion (i.e., limit state) can be shown on the capacity curve or on the simplified, equivalent bilinear capacity curve.

Commercial software usually uses either the N2 method or the Capacity Spectrum method to compare seismic demand and capacity in an Acceleration-Displacement Response Spectrum (ADRS) graph (Fig. 2.13).

If the software is based on the N2 method (Fig. 2.13a), the original demand is defined by the elastic response spectrum for the site and the design earthquake for the considered limit state. The elastic spectrum is then converted into an inelastic spectrum, based on the period of vibration of the idealised SDOF system response (T^*) and the equal energy (if $T^* < T_C$) or equal displacement (if $T^* \geq T_C$) criteria. The intersection of the inelastic demand spectrum and the

idealised SDOF response curve gives the target point, which indicates the expected displacement and damage in the structure for the considered seismic load.

On the other hand, if the software uses the Capacity Spectrum Method (Fig. 2.13b), the demand spectrum is damped according to the equivalent viscous damping of the structure at the attainment of the specified target displacement. Analytical formulations are provided in codes and literature to calculate the damping of masonry structures, which usually increases asymptotically with the target displacement, within the range of 5% to 20%. The target point is defined by the intersection of the damped demand spectrum with the capacity curve.

In both approaches, the structure withstands the design earthquake if the target point, representing demand, is to the left of the performance point, representing capacity.

Fig. 2.13 Example of capacity curve by (a) the N2- method and (b) the Capacity spectrum method.

2.6. Local behaviour (out-of-plane)

Out-of-plane (OOP) bending action induced by seismic loads may trigger local damage or collapse. Such damage is very dangerous, as the resulting debris poses a threat to people and property. The risk of local collapse is highest for structures without ties, in cases of poorly laid masonry, which tends to disaggregate, and in multiple-leaf masonry with unconnected leaves. OOP failure is very difficult to predict, because OOP loads are highest at the top floors, but post-earthquake observations show that OOP failure often occurs only after walls have been damaged by in-plane loads.

The application of CONSTRAIN strengthening is an effective strategy to prevent out-of-plane collapse of masonry walls, as the FRP material on the tension side increases the bending strength of the masonry cross-section. Furthermore, CONSTRAIN strengthening inherently provides tying and improves the connection of the wall leaves. It is especially effective in the case of two-sided coating, which almost entirely prevents out-of-plane collapse.

The problem of calculating the OOP bending resistance of a CRM-strengthened masonry cross-section at a given axial load is very similar to designing a reinforced concrete section, and can be evaluated on the basis of the following assumptions:

- composite action of CRM coating and the masonry (monolithic cross-section);
- planar sections remain planar (Bernoulli hypothesis);
- zero tensile strength of masonry;
- bilinear response of masonry in compression (Fig. 2.16a);
- zero compressive strength of fibres;
- linear response of fibres in tension, up to fracture (Fig. 2.16b);
- the contribution of the mortar, in tension (and, to be on the safe side, also in compression), is neglected;

Fig. 2.14 The constitutive law of masonry (a) and of fibers (b).

Failure due to masonry crushing or reaching the limit tensile strain of the fibres (with masonry in either the elastic or plastic stage) can occur, depending on the mechanical characteristics of the masonry and CRM, the wall thickness, and the applied axial load. For the out-of-plane bending resistance mechanism to activate, the masonry should not fail prematurely in shear at the cracked sections.

Any software for cross-section design may be used if it supports the constitutive models shown in Fig. 2.14. If such software is unavailable, analytical expressions may be used. The three cases are distinguished (Fig. 2.15), and the solution is the lowest value among them.

- *Type I*: masonry crushing at the compressive edge and fibers in the elastic range;
- *Type II*: tensile fracture of fibers and masonry compressive strain in the plateau;
- *Type III*: tensile fracture of fibers and linear stress distribution of masonry in compression.

Fig. 2.15 Strain and stress distribution into the CRM strengthened masonry cross section, for the three different cases.

Once CONSTRAIN strengthening is applied, failure occurs over the height of a storey. One possible approach to estimate the OOP capacity of walls is to assume one of the mechanisms shown in Fig. 2.16. The beneficial effect of vertical stress can be taken into account.

The mechanisms in Fig. 2.16 show that, particularly for CRM one-sided applications, ensuring the continuity of the reinforcement is crucial, so that the CRM reinforcement remains effective even when deflection occurs towards the unstrengthened surface. Adequate transverse anchoring is also important to prevent wall disintegration.

Fig. 2.16 Possible mechanisms for estimating OOP capacity of walls (piers) between two stories. (a) and (b) are cases of floors that have strong connection at the base and bottom, (c) is the case of top floor with flexible connection at the top.

3. Examples

Some application examples of calculations for piers and spandrels are presented. The calculations are based on the equations presented in §**Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**

Comparisons are made to the samples experimentally tested within the CONSTRAIN project.

3.1. Piers

3.1.1. Calculations

In this section the nonlinear response of a pier is calculated by an analytical model. To make the calculation as clear as possible, it is done by inserting numbers into the equations. The results are compared to an experimentally measured actual response of a masonry pier (the Constrain test P-R2-R1) to demonstrate the efficiency of the procedure.

The dimensions of the pier are presented in Fig. 3.1.

Fig. 3.1 Geometry of the rubble stone masonry pier.

- Stiffness

$$K_{P,e} = \frac{1}{\frac{h_p^3}{\eta EI} + \frac{h_p}{GA_s}} = \frac{1}{\frac{(1960 \text{ mm})^3}{12 \cdot 1931 \text{ MPa} \cdot 9.84 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ mm}^4} + \frac{1960 \text{ mm}}{666 \text{ MPa} \cdot 437500 \text{ mm}^2}} = \underline{\underline{99631 \text{ N/mm}}}$$

$$E = \frac{E_m t + E_c t_c}{t} = \frac{1074 \text{ MPa} \cdot 350 \text{ mm} + 10000 \text{ MPa} \cdot 30 \text{ mm}}{350 \text{ mm}} = \underline{\underline{1931 \text{ MPa}}}$$

$$I = \frac{t \cdot l_p^3}{12} = \frac{350 \text{ mm} \cdot (1500 \text{ mm})^3}{12} = \underline{\underline{9.84 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ mm}^4}}$$

$$G = \frac{G_m t + G_c t_c}{t} = \frac{0.3 \cdot 1074 \text{ MPa} \cdot 350 \text{ mm} + 4000 \text{ MPa} \cdot 30 \text{ mm}}{350 \text{ mm}} = \mathbf{666 \text{ MPa}}$$

$$A_s = \frac{t \cdot l_p}{1.2} = \frac{350 \text{ mm} \cdot 1500 \text{ mm}}{1.2} = \mathbf{437500 \text{ mm}^2}$$

• Lateral resistance

$$V_{P(\text{CRM})} = \min \left\{ \begin{array}{l} V_{P,d(\text{CRM})} \\ V_{P,f(\text{CRM})} \\ 0.25 l_p t f_m \end{array} \right. = \min \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 161.0 \text{ kN} \\ 197.1 \text{ kN} \\ 0.25 \cdot 1500 \text{ mm} \cdot 350 \text{ mm} \cdot 2.48 \text{ MPa} \end{array} \right. = \min \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 161.0 \text{ kN} \\ 197.1 \text{ kN} \\ 325.5 \text{ kN} \end{array} \right. = \mathbf{161.0 \text{ kN}}$$

$$V_{P,d(\text{CRM})} = V_{P,d(\text{URM})} + \chi \frac{1}{\gamma} \cdot i \cdot A_{\text{Fib}} \cdot n_{\text{Fib}} \cdot \varepsilon_{\text{lim,Fib}} \cdot E_{\text{Fib}} =$$

$$= 102100 \text{ N} + 1 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cdot 1 \cdot 8.8 \text{ mm}^2 \cdot 23 \cdot 0.0185 \cdot 31443 \text{ MPa} = \mathbf{161.0 \text{ kN}}$$

$$V_{P,d(\text{URM})} = \frac{1.5 \tau_0}{\beta} l_p t \sqrt{1 + \frac{\sigma_0}{1.5 \tau_0}} =$$

$$= \frac{1.5 \cdot 0.071 \text{ MPa}}{1.31} \cdot 1500 \text{ mm} \cdot 350 \text{ mm} \cdot \sqrt{1 + \frac{0.5 \text{ MPa}}{1.5 \cdot 0.071 \text{ MPa}}} =$$

$$= \mathbf{102.1 \text{ kN}}$$

$$\beta = \frac{h_p}{l_p} = \frac{1960 \text{ mm}}{1500 \text{ mm}} = \mathbf{1.31}$$

$$\sigma_0 = \frac{N}{l_p t} = \frac{262500 \text{ N}}{1500 \text{ mm} \cdot 350 \text{ mm}} = \mathbf{0.50 \text{ MPa}}$$

$$n_{\text{Fib}} = \frac{\min(h_p, l_p)}{s} = \frac{\min(1960 \text{ mm}, 1500 \text{ mm})}{66 \text{ mm}} = 22,7 \Rightarrow \mathbf{23}$$

$$V_{P,f(\text{CRM})} = \frac{\alpha M_{P,Rd(\text{CRM})}}{h_p} = \frac{2 \cdot 193.5 \text{ kNm}}{1.96 \text{ m}} = \mathbf{197.4 \text{ kN}}$$

$$M_{P,Rd(\text{CRM})} = \min \left\{ \begin{array}{l} M_{P,Rd}^I(N_{P,d}) \\ M_{P,Rd}^{II}(N_{P,d}) \\ M_{P,Rd}^{III}(N_{P,d}) \end{array} \right. = \min \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 214.6 \text{ kNm} \\ 193.5 \text{ kNm} \\ 222.2 \text{ kNm} \end{array} \right. = \mathbf{193.5 \text{ kNm}}$$

$$M_{P,Rd}^I = f_{m,cd} \frac{t y_n}{2} \left[l_p (1 - k) - y_n (1 - k)^2 + k \left(\frac{l_p}{2} - y_n + \frac{2}{3} k y_n \right) \right]$$

$$+ \frac{\varepsilon_{m,u}}{y_n} E_{\text{Fib}} t_{2,\text{Fib}} \frac{(d_{\text{Fib}} - y_n)^2}{12} (2y_n + 4d_{\text{Fib}} - 3l_p) =$$

$$= 2.48 \text{ MPa} \cdot \frac{350 \text{ mm} \cdot 427 \text{ mm}}{2}$$

$$\cdot \left[1500 \text{ mm} \cdot (1 - 0.19) - 427 \text{ mm} \cdot (1 - 0.19)^2 + 0.19 \right.$$

$$\cdot \left. \left(\frac{1500 \text{ mm}}{2} - 427 \text{ mm} + \frac{2}{3} \cdot 0.19 \cdot 427 \text{ mm} \right) \right] + \frac{0.012}{427 \text{ mm}}$$

$$\cdot 36400 \text{ MPa} \cdot 0.12 \text{ mm}$$

$$\cdot \frac{(1500 \text{ mm} - 427 \text{ mm})^2}{12} (2 \cdot 427 \text{ mm} + 4 \cdot 1500 \text{ mm} - 3$$

$$\cdot 1500 \text{ mm}) = \frac{214600000 \text{ Nmm}}{1000000} = \mathbf{214.6 \text{ kNm}}$$

$$k = \frac{\varepsilon_{m,y}}{\varepsilon_{m,u}} = \frac{0.0023}{0.012} = 0.19$$

$$y_n = \frac{N_{P,d} - E_{Fib} t_{2,Fib} d_{Fib} \varepsilon_{m,u} + \sqrt{N_{P,d}^2 + E_{Fib} t_{2,Fib} d_{Fib} \varepsilon_{m,u} [(2-k)t \cdot d_{Fib} f_{m,cd} - 2N_{P,d}]}}{t f_{m,cd} (2-k) - E_{Fib} t_{2,Fib} \varepsilon_{m,u}} =$$

$$= \frac{2623500 \text{ N} - 36400 \text{ MPa} \cdot 0.12 \text{ mm} \cdot 1500 \text{ mm} \cdot 0.012}{350 \text{ mm} \cdot 2.48 \text{ MPa} \cdot (2 - 0.19) - 36400 \text{ MPa} \cdot 0.12 \text{ mm} \cdot 0.012}$$

$$+ \frac{\sqrt{(262500 \text{ N})^2 + 36400 \text{ MPa} \cdot 0.12 \text{ mm} \cdot 1500 \text{ mm} \cdot 0.012 \cdot [(2 - 0.19) \cdot 350 \text{ mm} \cdot 1500 \text{ mm} \cdot 2.48 \text{ MPa} - 2 \cdot 2623500 \text{ N}]}}{350 \text{ mm} \cdot 2.48 \text{ MPa} \cdot (2 - 0.19) - 36400 \text{ MPa} \cdot 0.12 \text{ mm} \cdot 0.012}$$

$$= 427 \text{ mm}$$

$$M_{P,Rd}^{II} = f_{m,cd} \frac{t}{12} [2d_{Fib} y_n \xi (2\xi + 3) + 3l_p [y_n (2 + \xi) - \xi d_{Fib}] - 2y_n^2 (\xi^2 + 3 + 3\xi) - 2\xi^2 d_{Fib}^2]$$

$$+ \varepsilon_{lim,Fib} E_{Fib} t_{2,Fib} \frac{d_{Fib} - y_n}{12} (2y_n + 4d_{Fib} - 3l_p)$$

$$= 2.48 \text{ MPa} \cdot \frac{350 \text{ mm}}{12} [2 \cdot 1500 \text{ mm} \cdot 420 \text{ mm} \cdot 0.12 \cdot (2 \cdot 0.12 + 3) + 3 \cdot 1500 \text{ mm} \cdot [420 \text{ mm} \cdot (2 + 0.12) - 0.12 \cdot 1500 \text{ mm}] - 2 \cdot (420 \text{ mm})^2 \cdot (0.12^2 + 3 + 3 \cdot 0.12) - 3 \cdot 0.12^2 \cdot (1500 \text{ mm})^2] + 0.02 \cdot 36400 \text{ MPa} \cdot 0.12 \cdot \frac{1500 \text{ mm} - 420 \text{ mm}}{12} (2 \cdot 420 \text{ mm} + 4 \cdot 1500 \text{ mm} - 3 \cdot 1500 \text{ mm}) = \frac{193500000 \text{ Nmm}}{1000000}$$

$$= 193.5 \text{ kNm}$$

$$\xi = \frac{\varepsilon_{m,y}}{\varepsilon_{lim,Fib}} = \frac{0.0023}{0.02} = 0.12$$

$$y_n = \frac{2 \cdot N_{P,d} + t \xi f_{m,cd} \cdot d_{Fib} + E_{Fib} t_{2,Fib} d_{Fib} \varepsilon_{lim,Fib}}{t f_{m,cd} (2 + \xi) + E_{Fib} t_{2,Fib} \varepsilon_{lim,Fib}} =$$

$$= \frac{2 \cdot 262500 \text{ N} + 350 \text{ mm} \cdot 0.12 \cdot 2.48 \text{ MPa} \cdot 1500 \text{ mm} + 36400 \text{ MPa} \cdot 0.12 \text{ mm} \cdot 1500 \text{ mm} \cdot 0.02}{350 \text{ mm} \cdot 2.48 \text{ MPa} \cdot (2 + 0.12) + 36400 \text{ MPa} \cdot 0.12 \text{ mm} \cdot 0.02} =$$

$$= 420 \text{ mm}$$

$$M_{P,Rd}^{III} = \frac{t E_m \varepsilon_{lim,Fib}}{12} \frac{y_n^2}{d_{Fib} - y_n} (3l_p - 2y_n) + \varepsilon_{lim,Fib} E_{Fib} t_{2,Fib} \frac{d_{Fib} - y_n}{12} (2y_n + 4d_{Fib} - 3l_p) =$$

$$= \frac{350 \text{ mm} \cdot 36400 \text{ MPa} \cdot 0.02}{12} \cdot \frac{(315 \text{ mm})^2}{1500 \text{ mm} - 315 \text{ mm}} (3 \cdot 1500 \text{ mm} - 2 \cdot 315 \text{ mm}) + 0.02 \cdot 36400 \text{ MPa} \cdot 0.12 \text{ mm} \cdot \frac{1500 \text{ mm} - 315 \text{ mm}}{12} (2 \cdot 315 \text{ mm} + 4 \cdot 1500 \text{ mm} - 3 \cdot 1500 \text{ mm}) =$$

$$= \frac{222200000 \text{ Nmm}}{1000000} = 222.2 \text{ kNm}$$

$$y_n = \frac{N_{P,d} + E_{Fib} t_{2,Fib} d_{Fib} \cdot \varepsilon_{lim,Fib} - \sqrt{N_{P,d}^2 + E_m \varepsilon_{lim,Fib} d_{Fib} t (E_{Fib} t_{2,Fib} d_{Fib} \varepsilon_{lim,Fib} + 2N_{P,d})}}{\varepsilon_{lim,Fib} (E_{Fib} t_{2,Fib} - t E_m)} =$$

$$= \frac{262500 \text{ N} + 36400 \text{ MPa} \cdot 0.12 \text{ mm} \cdot 1500 \text{ mm} \cdot 0.02}{0.02 \cdot (36400 \text{ MPa} \cdot 0.12 \text{ mm} - 350 \text{ mm} \cdot 1074 \text{ MPa})}$$

$$= \frac{\sqrt{(262500 \text{ N})^2 + 1074 \text{ MPa} \cdot 0.02 \cdot 1500 \text{ mm} \cdot 350 \text{ mm} \cdot (36400 \text{ MPa} \cdot 0.12 \text{ mm} \cdot 1500 \text{ mm} \cdot 0.02 + 2 \cdot 262500 \text{ N})}}{0.02 \cdot (36400 \text{ MPa} \cdot 0.12 \text{ mm} - 350 \text{ mm} \cdot 1074 \text{ MPa})}$$

$$= 315 \text{ mm}$$

- Elastic displacement

$$d_{p,y(CRM)} = \frac{V_{P(CRM)}}{K_{P,e}} = \frac{161000 \text{ N}}{99631 \text{ N/mm}} = \underline{\underline{1.6 \text{ mm}}}$$

- Ultimate displacement

$$d_{p,u(CRM)} = \begin{cases} 0.010 h_p, & \text{if } V_{P,d(CRM)} < V_{P,f(CRM)} \\ 0.020 h_p, & \text{if } V_{P,d(CRM)} \geq V_{P,f(CRM)} \end{cases} = 0.010 \cdot 1960 \text{ mm} = \underline{\underline{19.6 \text{ mm}}}$$

3.1.2. Comparison to the experiment

The calculated response is graphically shown in Fig. 3.2. The calculated bilinear curve is shown in black, and the experimental curve is shown in green (average backbone curve for push and pull direction). The calculated response reasonably aligns with the experiment.

The design response of the pier is plotted by a dashed line in Fig. 3.2. To obtain design values, the compressive and tensile strength were divided by partial material safety factor $\gamma_M=1.5$.

The design response is conservative in comparison with the experiment.

Fig. 3.2: Comparison of nonlinear analytical response and experiment for P-R2-R1.

The analytical nonlinear response of unstrengthened rubble stone masonry pier P-R2-U is compared to the experiment in Fig. 3.3. The alignment of the results is reasonable and the design response is conservative.

Comparison of nonlinear response of rubble stone masonry pier strengthened on both sides (P-R2-R2) is compared to the experiment in Fig. 3.4. Again, the alignment between the responses is reasonable. The design displacement could perhaps be even larger, closer to a flexural collapse, which is imminent.

Fig. 3.3: Comparison of nonlinear analytical response and experiment for P-R2-U.

Fig. 3.4: Comparison of nonlinear analytical response and experiment for P-R2-R2.

• Lateral resistance

$$V_S = \min \left\{ \begin{array}{l} V_{S,d(CRM)} \\ V_{S,f(CRM)} \\ 0.25 b t_m f_m \end{array} \right. = \min \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 75.5 \text{ kN} \\ 47.8 \text{ kN} \\ 0.25 \cdot 1000 \text{ mm} \cdot 350 \text{ mm} \cdot 2.48 \text{ MPa} \end{array} \right. = \min \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 75.5 \text{ kN} \\ 47.8 \text{ kN} \\ 217 \text{ kN} \end{array} \right. = \underline{\underline{47.8 \text{ kN}}}$$

$$V_{S,d(CRM)} = V_{S,d(URM)} + \chi \frac{1}{\gamma} \cdot i \cdot \frac{A_G}{s} \cdot l_f \cdot \epsilon_{lim,G} \cdot E_G =$$

$$= 35500 \text{ N} + 1 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cdot 1 \cdot \frac{8 \text{ mm}^2}{66 \text{ mm}} \cdot 1000 \text{ mm} \cdot 0.02 \cdot 36400 \text{ MPa} = \mathbf{82.1 \text{ kN}}$$

$$V_{S,d(URM)} = \frac{1.5 \tau_0}{\beta} h_{st} \sqrt{1 + \frac{\sigma_0}{1.5 \tau_0}} =$$

$$= \frac{1.5 \cdot 0.071 \text{ MPa}}{1.05} \cdot 1000 \text{ mm} \cdot 350 \text{ mm} \cdot \sqrt{1 + \frac{0 \text{ MPa}}{1.5 \cdot 0.071 \text{ MPa}}} =$$

$$= \mathbf{35.5 \text{ kN}}$$

$$\beta = \frac{l}{h_S} = \frac{1050 \text{ mm}}{1000 \text{ mm}} = \mathbf{1.05}$$

$$\sigma_0 = \frac{N}{h_{st}} = \frac{0 \text{ N}}{1000 \text{ mm} \cdot 350 \text{ mm}} = \mathbf{0 \text{ MPa}}$$

$$V_{S,f(CRM)} = \frac{\alpha M_{S,Rd(CRM)}}{l_S} = \frac{2 \cdot 23.5 \text{ kNm}}{1.05 \text{ m}} = \mathbf{44.7 \text{ kN}}$$

$$M_{S,Rd(CRM)} = \min \left\{ \begin{array}{l} M_{S,Rd}^I(N_{S,d}) \\ M_{S,Rd}^{II}(N_{S,d}) \\ M_{S,Rd}^{III}(N_{S,d}) \end{array} \right. = \min \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 79.0 \text{ kNm} \\ 23.5 \text{ kNm} \\ 24.6 \text{ kNm} \end{array} \right. = \mathbf{23.5 \text{ kNm}}$$

$$M_{S,Rd}^I = f_{m,cd} \frac{t y_n}{2} \left[h_S (1 - k) - y_n (1 - k)^2 + k \left(\frac{h_S}{2} - y_n + \frac{2}{3} k y_n \right) \right]$$

$$+ \frac{\epsilon_{m,u}}{y_n} E_{Fib} t_{2,Fib} \frac{(d_{Fib} - y_n)^2}{12} (2 y_n + 4 d_{Fib} - 3 h_S) =$$

$$= 2.48 \text{ MPa} \cdot \frac{350 \text{ mm} \cdot 155 \text{ mm}}{2}$$

$$\cdot \left[1000 \text{ mm} \cdot (1 - 0.19) - 155 \text{ mm} \cdot (1 - 0.19)^2 + 0.19 \right.$$

$$\cdot \left. \left(\frac{1000 \text{ mm}}{2} - 155 \text{ mm} + \frac{2}{3} \cdot 0.19 \cdot 155 \text{ mm} \right) \right] + \frac{0.012}{155 \text{ mm}}$$

$$\cdot 31443 \text{ MPa} \cdot 0.14 \text{ mm}$$

$$\cdot \frac{(1000 \text{ mm} - 155 \text{ mm})^2}{12} (2 \cdot 155 \text{ mm} + 4 \cdot 1000 \text{ mm} - 3$$

$$\cdot 1000 \text{ mm}) = \frac{79000000 \text{ Nmm}}{1000000} = \mathbf{79.0 \text{ kNm}}$$

$$k = \frac{\epsilon_{m,y}}{\epsilon_{m,u}} = \frac{0.0023}{0.012} = \mathbf{0.19}$$

$$y_n = \frac{N_{S,d} - E_{Fib} t_{2,Fib} d_{Fib} \varepsilon_{m,u} + \sqrt{N_{S,d}^2 + E_{Fib} t_{2,Fib} d_{Fib} \varepsilon_{m,u} [(2-k)t \cdot d_{Fib} f_{m,cd} - 2N_{S,d}]}}{t f_{m,cd} (2-k) - E_{Fib} t_{2,Fib} \varepsilon_{m,u}} =$$

$$= \frac{350 \text{ mm} \cdot 2.48 \text{ MPa} \cdot (2 - 0.19) - 31443 \text{ MPa} \cdot 0.14 \text{ mm} \cdot 0.012}{0 \text{ N} - 31443 \text{ MPa} \cdot 0.14 \text{ mm} \cdot 1000 \text{ mm} \cdot 0.012}$$

$$+ \frac{\sqrt{(0 \text{ N})^2 + 31443 \text{ MPa} \cdot 0.14 \text{ mm} \cdot 1000 \text{ mm} \cdot 0.012 \cdot [(2 - 0.19) \cdot 350 \text{ mm} \cdot 1000 \text{ mm} \cdot 2.48 \text{ MPa} - 2 \cdot 0 \text{ N}]}}{350 \text{ mm} \cdot 2.48 \text{ MPa} \cdot (2 - 0.19) - 31443 \text{ MPa} \cdot 0.14 \text{ mm} \cdot 0.012}$$

$$= 155 \text{ mm}$$

$$M_{S,Rd}^{II} = f_{m,cd} \frac{t}{12} [2d_{Fib} y_n \xi (2\xi + 3) + 3h_s [y_n (2 + \xi) - \xi d_{Fib}] - 2y_n^2 (\xi^2 + 3 + 3\xi) - 3\xi^2 d_{Fib}^2]$$

$$+ \varepsilon_{lim,Fib} E_{Fib} t_{2,Fib} \frac{d_{Fib} - y_n}{12} (2y_n + 4d_{Fib} - 3h_s) =$$

$$= 2.48 \text{ MPa}$$

$$\cdot \frac{350 \text{ mm}}{12} [2 \cdot 1000 \text{ mm} \cdot 99 \text{ mm} \cdot 0.12 \cdot (2 \cdot 0.12 + 3) + 3 \cdot 1000 \text{ mm}$$

$$\cdot [99 \text{ mm} \cdot (2 + 0.12) - 0.12 \cdot 1000 \text{ mm}] - 2 \cdot (99 \text{ mm})^2 \cdot (0.12^2 + 3 + 3 \cdot 0.12)$$

$$- 3 \cdot 0.12^2 \cdot (1000 \text{ mm})^2] + 0.0185 \cdot 31443 \text{ MPa} \cdot 0.14 \text{ mm}$$

$$\cdot \frac{1500 \text{ mm} - 99 \text{ mm}}{12} (2 \cdot 99 \text{ mm} + 4 \cdot 1000 \text{ mm} - 3 \cdot 1000 \text{ mm}) = \frac{23500000 \text{ Nmm}}{1000000}$$

$$= 23.5 \text{ kNm}$$

$$\xi = \frac{\varepsilon_{m,y}}{\varepsilon_{lim,Fib}} = \frac{0.0023}{0.02} = 0.12$$

$$y_n = \frac{2 \cdot N_{S,d} + t \xi f_{m,cd} \cdot d_{Fib} + E_{Fib} t_{2,Fib} d_{Fib} \varepsilon_{lim,Fib}}{t f_{m,cd} (2 + \xi) + E_{Fib} t_{2,Fib} \varepsilon_{lim,Fib}} =$$

$$= \frac{2 \cdot 0 \text{ N} + 350 \text{ mm} \cdot 0.12 \cdot 2.48 \text{ MPa} \cdot 1000 \text{ mm} + 31443 \text{ MPa} \cdot 0.14 \text{ mm} \cdot 1000 \text{ mm} \cdot 0.0185}{350 \text{ mm} \cdot 2.48 \text{ MPa} \cdot (2 + 0.12) + 31443 \text{ MPa} \cdot 0.14 \text{ mm} \cdot 0.0185}$$

$$= 99 \text{ mm}$$

$$M_{S,Rd}^{III} = \frac{t E_m \varepsilon_{lim,Fib}}{12} \frac{y_n^2}{d_{Fib} - y_n} (3h_s - 2y_n) + \varepsilon_{lim,Fib} E_{Fib} t_{2,Fib} \frac{d_{Fib} - y_n}{12} (2y_n + 4d_{Fib} - 3h_s) =$$

$$= \frac{350 \text{ mm} \cdot 31443 \text{ MPa} \cdot 0.0185}{12} \cdot \frac{(98 \text{ mm})^2}{1000 \text{ mm} - 98 \text{ mm}} (3 \cdot 1000 \text{ mm} - 2 \cdot 98 \text{ mm}) + 0.0185$$

$$\cdot 31443 \text{ MPa} \cdot 0.14 \text{ mm} \cdot \frac{1000 \text{ mm} - 98 \text{ mm}}{12} (2 \cdot 98 \text{ mm} + 4 \cdot 1000 \text{ mm} - 3 \cdot 1000 \text{ mm}) =$$

$$= \frac{24600000 \text{ Nmm}}{1000000} = 24.6 \text{ kNm}$$

$$y_n = \frac{N_{S,d} + E_{Fib} t_{2,Fib} d_{Fib} \cdot \varepsilon_{lim,Fib} - \sqrt{N_{S,d}^2 + E_m \varepsilon_{lim,Fib} d_{Fib} t (E_{Fib} t_{2,Fib} d_{Fib} \varepsilon_{lim,Fib} + 2N_{S,d})}}{\varepsilon_{lim,Fib} (E_{Fib} t_{2,Fib} - t E_m)} =$$

$$= \frac{0 \text{ N} + 31443 \text{ MPa} \cdot 0.14 \text{ mm} \cdot 1000 \text{ mm} \cdot 0.0185}{0.0185 \cdot (31443 \text{ MPa} \cdot 0.14 \text{ mm} - 98 \text{ mm} \cdot 1074 \text{ MPa})}$$

$$- \frac{\sqrt{(0 \text{ N})^2 + 1074 \text{ MPa} \cdot 0.0185 \cdot 1000 \text{ mm} \cdot 350 \text{ mm} \cdot (31443 \text{ MPa} \cdot 0.14 \text{ mm} \cdot 1000 \text{ mm} \cdot 0.0185 + 2 \cdot 0 \text{ N})}}{0.0185 \cdot (31443 \text{ MPa} \cdot 0.14 \text{ mm} - 350 \text{ mm} \cdot 1074 \text{ MPa})}$$

$$= 98 \text{ mm}$$

- Elastic displacement

$$d_{S,y(CRM)} = \frac{V_{S,Rd}}{K_{S,e}} = \frac{44700 \text{ N}}{140335 \text{ N/mm}} = \underline{\underline{0.32 \text{ mm}}}$$

- Ultimate displacement

$$d_{S,u(CRM)} = 0.030 l_S = 0.030 \cdot 1050 \text{ mm} = \underline{\underline{31.5 \text{ mm}}}$$

3.2.2. Comparison to the experiment

The calculated response is graphically shown in Fig. 3.6. The calculated bilinear curve is shown in black, and the experimental curve is shown in green (average backbone curve for push and pull direction). Although the resistance of the analytical model is underestimated compared to the experiment, the calculated response reasonably aligns with the experiment.

The design response of the pier is plotted by a dashed line in Fig. 3.6. To obtain design values, the compressive and tensile strength were divided by partial material safety factor $\gamma_M=1.5$. The design response is even more conservative in comparison with the experiment.

Fig. 3.6 Comparison of pushover curve of analytical model and experiment of S-R2-R1.

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- [2] MIT - Ministero delle Infrastrutture e dei Trasporti. Circolare 21 gennaio 2019, n. 7 C.S.LL.PP.: Istruzioni per l'applicazione dell'«Aggiornamento delle “Norme tecniche per le costruzioni”» di cui al decreto ministeriale 17 gennaio 2018. 2019.
- [3] CNR DT 215/2018 Guide for the Design and Construction of Externally Bonded Fibre Reinforced Inorganic Matrix Systems for Strengthening Existing Structures.

Appendix A - List of symbols

Upper case letters:

A_{Fib}	Net area of fibres in a strand of FRP material
E	Equivalent elastic modulus of strengthened masonry
E_c	Elastic modulus of the mortar coating
E_{Fib}	Elastic modulus of fibres
E_m	Elastic modulus of masonry
G	Equivalent shear modulus of strengthened masonry
G_c	Shear modulus of mortar coating
G_m	Shear modulus of masonry
J	Second moment of area of the masonry cross-section
$K_{P,e}$	Initial (elastic) stiffness of pier
$K_{S,e}$	Initial (elastic) stiffness of spandrel
$M_{P,Rd(CRM)}$	Maximum resistance of pier to bending moment
$M_{P,Rd}^I$	Moment resistance of pier (type 1 failure)
$M_{P,Rd}^{II}$	Moment resistance of pier (type 2 failure)
$M_{P,Rd}^{III}$	Moment resistance of pier (type 3 failure)
$M_{S,Rd(CRM)}$	Maximum resistance of spandrel to bending moment
$M_{S,Rd}^I$	Moment resistance of spandrel (type 1 failure)
$M_{S,Rd}^{II}$	Moment resistance of spandrel (type 2 failure)
$M_{S,Rd}^{III}$	Moment resistance of spandrel (type 3 failure)
$M_{S,Rd(URM)}$	Resistance of URM spandrel to bending moment
$M_{S(URM+tie)}$	Resistance of semi-coupled strengthened spandrel to bending moment
$N_{P,d}$	Design axial (compressive) force in pier
$N_{S,d}$	Design axial (compressive) force in spandrel
V_P	Maximum in-plane resistance of pier to lateral force
$V_{P,d(CRM)}$	Resistance of strengthened pier to lateral force at diagonal shear failure
$V_{P,d(Fib)}$	Resistance provided by CRM coating to lateral force at diagonal shear failure
$V_{P,f(CRM)}$	Resistance of strengthened pier to lateral force at flexural failure
$V_{P(CRM)}$	Resistance of strengthened pier to in-plane lateral load
$V_{P(URM)}$	Resistance of URM pier to in-plane lateral load
$V_{P,d(URM)}$	Resistance of URM pier to lateral force at diagonal shear failure
V_S	Maximum in-plane resistance of spandrel to lateral force
$V_{S,d(CRM)}$	Resistance of spandrel to lateral force at diagonal shear failure
$V_{S,d(Fib)}$	Resistance provided by CRM coating to lateral force at diagonal shear failure
$V_{S,f(CRM)}$	Resistance of spandrel to lateral force at flexural failure
$V_{S(CRM)}$	Resistance of strengthened spandrel to in-plane lateral force
$V_{S(URM)}$	Resistance of URM spandrel to in-plane lateral load

Lower case letters:

d_{Fib}	Distance between extreme tension in strands and extreme compression in masonry
$d_{P,y}$	Maximum elastic displacement of pier
$d_{P,u}$	Ultimate displacement (i.e., displacement at near collapse) of pier
$d_{S,y}$	Maximum elastic displacement of spandrel
$d_{S,u}$	Ultimate displacement (i.e., displacement at near collapse) of spandrel
$f_{hm,cd}$	Design compressive strength of masonry in horizontal direction
$f_{m,cd}$	Design compressive strength of masonry
$f_{m,t}$	Tensile strength of masonry (obtained by diagonal compression test)
$f_{m,td}$	Design tensile strength of masonry (obtained by diagonal compression test)
$f_{t,eq}$	Equivalent masonry tensile strength
f_{v0}	Shear strength at zero compression (sliding shear along bed joints)
h_b	Brick or block height
h_P	Pier height
h_S	Height of the masonry part of the spandrel
i	Number of strengthened sides
l_{eff}	Effective length of interlocking at the spandrel extremities
l_{Fib}	Reference dimension of the pier/spandrel measured orthogonally to the shear force
l_P	Pier length (width)
l_S	Spandrel length
n_{Fib}	Number of horizontal strands of fibers crossing the diagonal crack
s	Strand spacing
t_c	Thickness of mortar coating
t	Thickness of masonry
t_{Fib}	Equivalent thickness of the tensile layer
y_n	Depth of neutral axis

Greek symbols:

α	Coefficient for boundary conditions
α_t	Reduction factor for fibres when stressed in shear
β	Slenderness ratio
$\varepsilon_{lim,Fib,d}$	Effective design tensile strain of fibres at failure
$\varepsilon_{m,y}$	Yield strain of masonry in compression
$\varepsilon_{m,u}$	Ultimate strain of masonry in compression
η	Coefficient for boundary conditions
λ	Reduction coefficient for the URM spandrel resistance after diagonal cracking
γ	Partial factor for the resistance model
χ	Reduction coefficient for unsymmetric reinforcement application
σ_0	Compressive stress in pier
σ_{P0}	Average compressive stress in the piers adjacent to the spandrel
τ_0	Shear strength at zero precompression
$\tau_{0,d}$	Design shear strength at zero precompression